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Influence of Gender and Location on Upper Basic Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour in Edo and Delta States

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of gender and location on Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. Two research questions were raised and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level. The population of the study was 51, 624. The sample size for the study was 720 respondents arrived at using the multi-stage sampling technique. The questionnaire is the instrument for data collection. Data generated were analyzed using the simple correlation statistics for the research questions while the simple regression was used to test the formulated null hypotheses. Findings of the study revealed amongst that, there was a significant relationship between gender and location as regards Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in the state under review. The study concluded that gender and location influences Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The study made appropriate recommendations for the study.

Keywords

Social Studies, Gender, location, Sexual Behaviour.

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Introduction

In today's society, the sexual behaviour of students is a vital issue that if not managed properly will give way to a detrimental effect on the child; as its sway on students can result in the engagement of risky sexual conduct that is capable of destroying the child's future and this is so for both male and female students in the society. There is evidence that students' sexual behavior is influenced by their gender. Frankel, Bass, Patterson, Dai, and Brown's (2018) research suggested that gender, fatherlessness are the main risk factors for students starting sex at a young age. Males were more likely than females to report never having had sex before the age of sixteen, according to Smith, Jackson, Vancampfort, Jacob, Firth, and Grabovac (2020), while Martin (2018) verified that boys were introduced to sex earlier than girls.

Additionally, gender variations in sexuality have long been the focus of study. According to a 1993–2007 meta-analysis, men were generally more accepting of other people's sexual orientations and reported having more sexual experiences than women. Adolescent sexuality and behavior exhibit gender-specific differences, and these distinctions are still evident in this stage of life (Seyfu&Yohannes, 2018). Gender discrimination and sexual development are impacted by the gender double standard (Martin, 2018). This means that, in contrast to girls, who are typically more sexually uninhibited due to their exposure to a peer environment that is more accepting of sex and places more pressure on them to engage in sexual activity, boys are typically more sexually uninhibited (Boilard, Van De Bongardt&Blais, 2016). Among a sizable sample of Spanish teenage students, a study examining gender variations in sexual behavior found that boys were more likely than girls to engage in risky sexual behaviors (such as having multiple sexual partners or not using contraception) in general.

However, Kreager's study's conclusions can be explained by environmental and geographic factors, as a school's location has a significant impact on students' sexual behavior. Students' sexual behavior in social studies is greatly influenced by the setting of the school. Schools in rural areas are more likely to have students who exhibit strong moral convictions. This is explained by the fact that, in contrast to urban settings where every amenity that promotes immorality is readily available for students to copy and internalize, students in rural areas are not exposed to as many influential variables in society that have the tendency to negatively sway students' morality.

According to Ojong, Ojong-Alasia, and Samson-Akpan (2014), in a study carried out in Rwanda, more than 11% of youth between the ages of 12 and 24 were infected. It was stated that among teenagers, infections were in fact more common in rural than in urban areas. Implicitly, given that it was reported that 80% of HIV/AIDS infections happen in rural areas. It's possible that the young people who contracted the virus in the countryside engaged in or were more sexually active than their counterparts in the cities. Therefore, an individual's sexual behavior can be positively or negatively impacted by the environment in which they live. Additionally, residents' lifestyles may differ significantly from those of urban dwellers. While people who live in rural areas might not have access to as much information, those who live in cities might benefit from it. Therefore, it makes sense that geographic location would have an impact on human behavior when studying students' sexual behaviour.

Statement of the Problem

The modern educational system is progressively changing from a place of learning to one of moral slackness, promiscuity, and sexual permissiveness. With reference to students sexual conduct. This behavior's explanation is not implausible. A number of factors, including gender of students and

their locational glamorization of sex and suggestive sexual scenes tends to contribute to the indulging in sexual behaviour before marriage; hence, this study sought to find out the influence of both gender – male and female and location – urban and rural with regards to their influence on social studies students in Edo and Delta States.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

- i. What is the relationship between gender and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?
- ii. What is the relationship between school location and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

- i. There is no significant relationship between gender and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between school location and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Gender and Students' Sexual Behaviour

It has been shown that gender-based norms in sub-Saharan African nations worsen the sexual and reproductive health outcomes of emerging adults (Bersamin, Zamboanga, Schwartz, Donnellan, Hudson, Weisskirch & Caraway, 2014). More often than we probably think, women are raised in a patriarchal environment where men are seen as superior in both social and romantic contexts (Maughan-Brown et al. 2018). In the same way, young women are subservient to men during sexual interactions. In contrast, men are assertive, confident, autonomous, and dominant when it comes to their sexual choices with women (Zuma et al. 2016). Women's ability to negotiate safer sexual relationships and reject unwanted ones is impacted by this skewed gender orientation (Evans et al. 2016; Igberaharha & Onyesom, 2021). As a result, unintended pregnancies, forced abortions, low self-esteem, and the spread of STDs like HIV/AIDS are widespread. This is due to the fact that their sexuality is mediated by gender-based and sociocultural norms (Schaefer et al. 2017).

Literature has shown that young people's sexual activity is influenced by gender power relations. For example, data from a study by Odimegwu & Somefun (2017) indicated that most women could access male condoms and demonstrated their own agency in sexual relationships. However, a greater proportion of men than women believed that it is inappropriate for a woman to get a male condom. In particular, the findings demonstrated that the relationship between attitudes toward gender roles and sexual behavior is still unclear. The authors came to the conclusion that research on sexual and gender norms is still inconsistent. They contended that the study's cross-sectional design might have an impact on the accuracy and degree to which attitudes toward gender roles and socio-demographic traits, which are explanatory variables, influenced sexual behavior. To be clear, the study's findings could be compromised by grouping variables to gauge attitudes toward gender roles. In conclusion, we proposed that qualitative research would offer a deeper understanding of the capacity of gender role attitudes to predict sexual behavior. As a result, this study aims to expand on the qualitative approach recommendations.

There aren't many studies conducted in Nigeria that examine how gender norms, values (Onyesom & Igberaharha, 2021) and sociocultural discourse influence emerging adults' ability to exercise their personal agency in pedagogy and in sexual relationships. Studies conducted in other

nations, however, revealed a high frequency of unintended pregnancies, induced abortions, STD transmission, and high school dropout rates. These findings were linked to sociocultural elements and gender norms that are ingrained in sexual relationships (Odimegwu et al. 2018). However, a number of quantitative studies conducted in Nigeria have found evidence of sex differences in young people's sexual behavior, not true gender constructs (Agunbiade&Aransiola, 2016).

Numerous quantitative studies found that women demonstrated more positive sexual behavior than men did. These academics contend that because of the social stigma associated with women's sexuality, women tend to respond in ways that are socially acceptable and undervalue their own sexual behavior. However, men may exaggerate their sexual behavior in an effort to assert their dominance and masculinity in romantic partnerships. In contrast to other studies (Agunbiade&Aransiola, 2016) that reported sex differentials in sexual behavior, this study examines the primary gender and socio-cultural nuances while omitting to consider gender and socio-cultural nuances from individual agency. Conceptually, this is incorrect because gender norms in sexual relationships are viewed as social constructs that address the nature of power dynamics in relationships, but not merely differences in sexual behaviour within the lens of sex as a biological difference.

Furthermore, a large body of research on young adults' sexual behavior conducted in Sub-Saharan African nations revealed variations in young people's sexuality. According to recent research, men are more likely than women to initiate sexual activity, use condoms, have multiple sexual partners, and be older when they have their first sex (Evans et al. 2016). However, academics contend that the prevalence of condom use among women may be underreported due to the stigma associated with disclosing sexual activity or that young women may not be inclined to talk about sensitive sexual issues that are not acceptable in society (Agunbiade&Aransiola, 2016). A meta-analysis study also revealed that men reported having more sexual partners than women. Girls did, however, report feeling more and having less pleasure, though this varies over time. Some girls encounter sexual assault during their first sexual encounter, which likely discourages them from seeking out and reports fewer sexual partners.

Males and females have different sexual attitudes and behaviors, with men being more permissive in this regard. Sexual permissiveness has serious health implications and jeopardizes gender equality in sexual relationships. Agunbiade and Aransiola(2016) discovered that men demonstrated more positive sexual behavior than women, including condom use. However, this might be the result of young women's subordination in sexual relationships due to their lower socioeconomic status, particularly if there is a significant age gap between them and older men.

Devine-Wright, Abraham, Onya, and Ramatsea conducted another study. Males were found to have more sexual partners than females, according to research by Themane and Aarø (2015). However, given that females may underreport their sexual activity as a sensitive matter, the results should be interpreted cautiously. Similarly, it has been established that younger men (15–24 years old) have more sexual partners than women. According to some data, men are more likely than women to have their first sexual experience (Haffejee et al. 2018). These studies exclusively looked at differences between male and female sexual behavior. However, a small number of studies examined sexual behaviour as well as major gender and cultural constructs. For example, the prevalence of male dominance in sexual behavior is consistent with patriarchal values and gender norms across various ethnic groups in Nigeria (Ngidi et al. 2016). This is similar to the findings in a study conducted in South Africa that reported girls indulged their boyfriends with sex so as to sustain relationships, and prevent advances from other females.

Males were found to have more sexual partners than females, according to research by Haffejee, Koorbanally & Corona (2018). However, given that females may underreport their sexual activity as a sensitive matter, the results should be interpreted cautiously. Similarly, it has been established that younger men (15–24 years old) have more sexual partners than women. According to some data, men are more likely than women to have their first sexual experience (Haffejee et al. 2018). These studies exclusively looked at differences between male and female sexual behavior. However, a small number of studies examined sexual behavior as well as major gender and cultural constructs. For example, the prevalence of male dominance in sexual behavior is consistent with patriarchal values and gender norms across various ethnic groups in Nigeria (Ngidi et al. 2016). Secondary school students make up the majority of young people in our society whose sexual behaviour is seriously concerning. This is the point at which some of these young people give up on their academic goals and jeopardize their future due to one irresponsible, foolish, or ill-timed sexual behavior, among other behaviors. Teenage unmarried people's sexual practices were once considered taboo in Nigeria and throughout Africa. Today's story is different, though, since teenagers freely engage in a variety of sexual behaviors. According to Opara (2008), referenced by Ojong, Ojong-Alasia, and Samson-Akpan (2014), in her research on the understanding and usage of human sexuality among students at Cross River University of Technology in Calabar, Nigeria, 60% of the participants had their first sexual experience as early as fourteen (14) years old. Out of 400 female students, only one declared herself to be a virgin in that study.

Additionally, a study by Okonko, Okerentugba, Adejuwon and Onoh, as reported by Ojong, Ojong-Alasia, and Samson-Akpan (2014), revealed that, of the 200 samples analyzed, 195 (97.5%) had growths of staphylococcus, and 5(2.5%) had infections from different etiologic agents. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2017) has released alarming reports regarding the rapid transmission of HIV among sexually active youth aged 15-24. Many of these young people attend secondary schools. The reports also emphasized that approximately 80% of infections in this age group and in adults are related to sexual activity. Because it deals with personal issues, studying sexual behavior is challenging. There are, nevertheless, a few empirical research.

704 single youth between the ages of 12 and 24 participated in an extensive study conducted by the researchers on the experiences of teenagers with sexual health in three Ghanaian towns. The findings indicated that 52% of all respondents had engaged in sexual activity. Additionally, the results indicated that young women had a higher likelihood of having had sexual experience than men did (56% versus 48%, respectively). According to the same study, 61% of participants thought that someone, especially an adolescent, could have a satisfying sexual relationship with a partner without engaging in penetrating vaginal sex. The noncontact behaviors or experiences mentioned included fondling, kissing, and toughing. Joshua (2006) enumerated the following sexual behaviors in a study on temperament, values, and sexual behavior among Cross River State secondary school students: attitudinal act, peripheral acts like masturbation, petting, kissing and actual sexual act engaged in by students in the various school locations across the study area.

Location and Students Sexual Behaviour

One's behavior can be positively or negatively impacted by the environment in which they live. Additionally, urban and rural residents may lead very different lifestyles. Rural residents might not have the same access to a wealth of information as their urban counterparts (Igberaharha, 2014; Ibrahim & Ihuoma, 2017). Therefore, it makes sense that geography would have an impact on how people behave. A student's location has a significant impact on how they behave sexually. This is true because the factors that shaped the sexuality of students in urban and rural areas differ. Because they

live in an urban or rural area of society, it is thought that urban students are more exposed to sexual content and avenues that support sexual content. As a result, it has a significant impact on how they feel about sexual behavior inside or outside of the school, as well as how it affects their general well-being (Joshua, 2006).

The decade of adolescence, which spans from 10 to 19 years old and represents the shift from childhood to adulthood, is a crucial turning point in every person's life. Adolescents make up around one-fifth (1.2 billion) of the world's population, with 85% of them living in developing nations like Africa, where they make up roughly 30% of the population overall. According to estimates from 2006, adolescents make up roughly 30% of the total population in Nigeria (Ibrahim & Ihuoma, 2017). The onset of adolescence is considered a crucial developmental transition, due to the confluence of changes that occur across this level of development. It is a period full of adventure in all sphere of human endeavours including sexual practices (Samson-Akpan, 2014). The sexual activities among adolescents in many countries and Nigeria in particular have resulted into unplanned/unwanted pregnancy, early childbearing, unsafe abortion and Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs) including Human Immunodeficiency virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS) amongst students in both the rural and urban area of the society.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design on a population of 51,624 Social Studies students in Edo and Delta States in the 2023/2024 academic session. The study employed two different sample techniques of the proportional random sampling technique and the stratified random sampling approaches respectively. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire used to elicit information from Social Studies students. The instrument produced a reliability index of 0.793, making it reliable for use in this study. The collated data were analyzed using the simple correlation statistics which was used to provide answers to the stated research questions. On the other hand, the simple regression (ANOVA) was used to test the formulated null hypotheses at an alpha of 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between gender and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour? Result is illustrated in a simple correlation Table

Table 1: Simple Correlation Analysis of Gender of Social Studies Students and Sexual Behaviour

Variables	N	r	r ²	r ^{2adj}	Independent Variable: Gender, Dependent Variable: Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour
Gender					
Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour	720	.027	.001	-.001	

Table 1 presents the simple correlation results where it revealed that gender of students as indicated by r-value of .027 shows a positive relationship between gender of Social Studies students and their sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. This provides an answer to research question 1. It revealed that there is a positive relationship between gender of students and their sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The r² adjusted value of -.001 indicated that gender of students can impact their sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between gender and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. Result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between Gender and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Score	($\bar{x}$)	f	t	Std Error	Sig
Regression	13590.322	1	5.949		.307	-.557	.330	.58
Residual	13596.326	719	19.196					
Total	13596.326	720						

P ≥ 0.05 level of significance; N = 720

As shown in Table 2, the computed ANOVA produced an F = .307, P ≥ 0.05. Since there is no discernible link between gender and students' attitudes toward sexual behavior in Edo and the Delta States' Upper Basic Social Studies curriculum, the null hypothesis was accepted. The results show that there is no discernible link between students' attitudes toward sexual behavior in Upper Basic Social Studies and their gender. The review concludes that there is no positive correlation between gender and the sexual behavior of students in the examined area.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between school location and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States? Result is illustrated in a simple correlation Table

Table 3: Simple Correlation Analysis of School Location and Social Studies Students sexual behaviour

Variables	N	r	r ²	r ^{2adj}
School Location				
Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour	720	.083	.008	.005

Independent Variable: School Location, Dependent Variable: Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour.

Table 3 presents the simple correlation results where it revealed that school location as indicated by r-value of .083 showed a positive relationship between school location and Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. This provides an answer to research question 2. It revealed that there is a positive relationship between school location and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The r² adjusted value of .005 indicated that school location has impact on Social Studies students' sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between school location and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta State. Result is presented in Table 4

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between school location and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Score	$\bar{X}$	f	t	Std Error	Sig
Regression	101.231	1	101.231		5.299	-2.305	.217	.02
Residual	13495.177	719	19.061					
Total	13495.177	720						

P ≤ 0.05 level of significance; N = 720

As shown in Table 4, the computed ANOVA produced an $F = 5.299$, $P \leq 0.05$. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between school location and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour is rejected. The finding is that there is a significant relationship between school location and social studies students towards sexual behaviour. The conclusion is reached that school location has positive relationship to sexual behaviour of students involved in this study.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis's result indicated that there was a noteworthy correlation between Upper Basic Social Studies students' gender and their attitudes toward sexual behavior. The point being made here is that the students' sexual behavior is influenced by their gender. The work of Olapegba, Idemudia, and Onuoha (2013), who discovered a significant gender difference in responsible sexual behavior ($t(246) = -4.08$; $p < .05$), provided momentum to this finding. Compared to male adolescents, female adolescents exhibited a significantly higher positive disposition toward responsible sexual behavior. The average age at first sexual encounter was higher for females (18 years) than for males (16 years), according to Mturi and Gaeawe's (2014) study, which further supports this finding by demonstrating that gender and year of study are significant determinants of age at first sex. Additionally, they concluded that, from a multivariate perspective, men are less likely than females to engage in risky sexual activities.

The outcome of hypothesis two showed that there was a noteworthy correlation between Upper Basic Social Studies and school location. Students' attitude toward sexual activity. This indicates that their sexual behavior was influenced by the study's location, whether it was rural or urban. This result is consistent with the research of Akpokos, Nkom and Oluwabamidele (2017), which discovered a substantial correlation between sexual behaviour in urban and rural settings. Specifically, premarital sex was found to be more common among male students attending urban schools than among their counterparts attending rural schools. It was discovered that female students from rural schools participated in the same sexual behaviour more frequently than their counterparts from urban schools. The results of this investigation, however, were at odds with those of Thompson, Mahony, Noble, and Wang's (2018) study, which concluded that there were no appreciable variations in the sexual behaviors of adolescents living in rural and urban areas. They did point out that the sexual intentions of adolescents in rural and urban areas varied, but they also agreed, albeit not entirely, that when it came to students' sexual behavior, students in rural areas were more likely than those in urban areas to plan to have sex without a condom in the upcoming year.

Conclusion

Adolescent sexual behaviour is unavoidable since it is a necessary stage of growth. Physiological, psychological, and social factors all play a role in its direction. Different findings have been reported by this investigation. This study shows that gender and location have considerable influence on students' sexual behaviour. Essentially, the research found that:

- i. Students' sexual behavior in Edo and Delta States is influenced by their gender in Upper Basic Social Studies classes.
- ii. School location of Upper Basic Social Studies Students influences their sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Recommendations

Following from the conclusion, the following recommendations were made that in a bid to prevent unintended pregnancies and STDs, Upper Basic Social Studies students should regularly receive education on safe behavioral approaches to sex and sexual outcomes. Also, when talking about teenage sexual behaviour in Nigeria, it is important to prioritize the effect of gender and location as they exact considerable influence on students with regards to the subject matter.

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